
EXPLORATION OF HOW SELF-DETERMINATION AND SOCIAL COGNITIVE THEORIES APPLY TO THE CONTEXT OF THE TOURISM FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: the tourism field of education encompasses a range of experiential learning opportunities, including internships, field trips, and practical training, aimed at preparing students for careers in the tourism industry. Self-determination theory and social cognitive theory offer valuable insights into the motivational factors and cognitive processes that influence learning and skill acquisition in this context. This study seeks to explore the application of these theories within tourism of field education.

Keywords: tourism, motivation, Self-Determination Theory (SDT), Social Cognitive Theory (SCT).

Introduction: Motivation plays a crucial role in language learning, influencing learners' engagement, persistence, and ultimately, their proficiency levels. Several theories of motivation provide valuable insights into understanding the factors that drive language learners. Two prominent theories in this regard are Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT).

The tourism field of education involves preparing students for careers in the dynamic and diverse tourism industry. Understanding motivational theories such as Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) is essential for designing effective educational programs and fostering students' success in this field.

Methods: *Self-Determination Theory*, proposed by Deci and Ryan, posits that individuals are inherently motivated to pursue activities that satisfy their basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. In the context of language learning, SDT highlights the importance of intrinsic motivation, which arises from within the individual, as opposed to extrinsic motivation, which stems from external rewards or pressures.

According to SDT, learners who perceive autonomy in their language learning process, such as having choices in selecting learning materials or approaches, are more likely to experience intrinsic motivation. Similarly, feelings of competence, achieved through mastering language skills and seeing progress, contribute to sustained motivation. Finally, a sense of relatedness, including positive relationships with teachers and peers, fosters a supportive learning environment that enhances motivation.

Research by Noels et al. has shown that autonomy-supportive teaching practices, such as providing meaningful choices and acknowledging students' perspectives, positively impact language learners' motivation and performance. Additionally, studies by Dörnyei and Ushioda emphasize the role of intrinsic motivation in maintaining long-term engagement and language learning success.

Social Cognitive Theory, proposed by Bandura, emphasizes the dynamic interplay between personal factors, environmental influences, and behavior in shaping motivation and learning. SCT posits that individuals learn not only through direct experiences but also by observing others and modeling their behaviors. In the context of language learning, SCT highlights the role of self-efficacy beliefs, outcome expectations, and observational learning in motivating learners.

Self-efficacy beliefs refer to individuals' beliefs in their own abilities to perform tasks and achieve desired outcomes. Language learners with high self-efficacy are more likely to set challenging goals, persist in the face of difficulties, and adopt effective learning strategies. Furthermore, outcome expectations, or beliefs about the consequences of language learning, influence learners' motivation levels. Positive outcome expectations, such as improved job opportunities or enhanced intercultural communication skills, can boost motivation.

Observational learning, another key aspect of SCT, suggests that learners can be motivated by observing the successful language learning experiences of others, including peers, teachers, or role models. By witnessing others' achievements and overcoming challenges, learners may increase their motivation and confidence in their own language learning abilities.

Research by Bandura and Zimmerman provides empirical support for the role of self-efficacy beliefs in predicting language learning outcomes and persistence. Additionally, studies by Kim have demonstrated the influence of observational learning on language learners' motivation and engagement in classroom settings.

Results: findings indicate that self-determination theory emphasizes the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation and engagement among tourism students. Students who perceive autonomy in their learning process, feel competent in their abilities, and have meaningful connections with peers and mentors are more likely to experience higher levels of motivation and satisfaction in the tourism field of education. Social cognitive theory highlights the role of observational learning, self-efficacy beliefs, and goal-setting in shaping students' learning experiences and performance outcomes. Through vicarious experiences and modeling, students develop confidence in their abilities and strive towards achieving mastery in tourism-related skills.

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) in the tourism field of education:

Self-determination theory emphasizes the importance of intrinsic motivation, autonomy, competence, and relatedness in driving individuals' engagement and persistence in learning. In the context of the tourism field of education, SDT can be applied to promote students' intrinsic motivation and enhance their learning experiences.

Autonomy: providing students with autonomy in their learning process can increase their motivation and engagement. In tourism education, educators can offer students opportunities to select research topics, choose fieldwork destinations, or design their own projects. By allowing students to take ownership of their learning, educators empower them to pursue areas of interest and develop a sense of responsibility for their education.

Competence: building students' competence is crucial for fostering their confidence and motivation in the tourism field. Educators can design learning activities that challenge students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical settings, such as internships, field trips, or simulated scenarios. Feedback and recognition of students' achievements further enhance their sense of competence and motivate them to strive for excellence.

Relatedness: creating a supportive learning environment where students feel connected to their peers, educators, and industry professionals is essential for promoting motivation in tourism education. Collaborative projects, group discussions, and networking opportunities allow students to interact with others who share their interests and aspirations. Peer mentoring programs and guest lectures from industry experts can also facilitate meaningful connections and provide students with valuable insights and encouragement.

Research by Chen and Hashimoto suggests that autonomy-supportive teaching practices in tourism education positively impact students' intrinsic motivation, academic engagement, and career aspirations. Similarly, studies by Kim and Pearce have shown that fostering a sense of relatedness and belongingness among tourism students contributes to their overall satisfaction with their educational experiences and future career intentions.

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) in the tourism field of education:

Social cognitive theory focuses on the reciprocal interactions between personal factors, environmental influences, and behavior. In the context of the tourism field of education, SCT can be applied to understand how students' beliefs, observations, and social interactions influence their motivation and learning outcomes.

Self-efficacy: according to SCT, students' beliefs in their own abilities to succeed in tourism-related tasks and challenges significantly impact their motivation and performance. Educators can enhance students' self-efficacy by providing opportunities for skill development, experiential learning, and role modeling. Practical experiences

such as internships, case studies, and industry placements allow students to apply theoretical knowledge and build confidence in their capabilities.

Outcome expectations: students' expectations about the outcomes of their education and future careers play a crucial role in motivating their engagement and effort. In the tourism field of education, educators can highlight the diverse career opportunities and potential rewards associated with a successful career in the industry. Guest lectures, alumni panels, and industry networking events expose students to real-world perspectives and experiences, helping them to envision their future roles and responsibilities in the tourism sector.

Observational learning: SCT emphasizes the role of observational learning, where students observe and model the behaviors and achievements of others in their learning environment. Educators can facilitate observational learning by showcasing success stories, sharing industry best practices, and providing opportunities for students to interact with industry professionals and alumni. Experiential learning opportunities, such as field trips, study tours, and internships, allow students to observe and learn from real-world examples and experiences.

Research by Kim et al. suggests that self-efficacy beliefs significantly predict students' academic performance and career intentions in tourism education. Similarly, studies by Wong and Chon have demonstrated the importance of outcome expectations and observational learning in shaping students' motivation and career aspirations in the tourism industry.

Discussion: the integration of self-determination theory and social cognitive theory into the tourism field of education offers valuable implications for curriculum design, instructional strategies, and student support services. Educators can leverage these theoretical frameworks to design experiential learning activities that promote autonomy, competence, and relatedness, while also fostering self-efficacy beliefs and goal-setting strategies. Moreover, by aligning educational objectives with industry demands and career aspirations, educators can better prepare students for success in the dynamic and competitive field of tourism.

Interactive activities play a pivotal role in language learning, as they have been shown to enhance motivation and engagement among learners. By encouraging active participation, fostering collaboration, and providing meaningful learning experiences, interactive activities contribute to a positive and dynamic learning environment. This discussion explores the various ways in which interactive activities can enhance motivation and engagement, drawing on research and scholarly sources.

Active participation and engagement: interactive activities require learners to actively participate in the learning process, promoting engagement and involvement. Unlike passive learning methods such as lectures or reading assignments, interactive activities encourage learners to interact with the language in meaningful ways.

Activities such as role-plays, group discussions, and language games provide opportunities for learners to practice language skills in authentic contexts, leading to increased motivation and engagement.

Research by Oxford and Shearin suggests that active participation in interactive activities fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility for learning outcomes, leading to greater engagement and investment in the learning process. Moreover, interactive activities stimulate curiosity and interest, motivating learners to explore and discover language concepts independently.

Immediate feedback and reinforcement: interactive activities often provide learners with immediate feedback on their performance, allowing them to monitor their progress and make adjustments in real-time. Feedback can come from peers, instructors, or through self-assessment mechanisms integrated into the activity. This immediate feedback loop enhances motivation by reinforcing correct responses and addressing misconceptions or errors promptly.

According to Hattie and Timperley, feedback that is specific, timely, and actionable is particularly effective in promoting learning and motivation. Interactive activities facilitate the provision of personalized feedback tailored to individual learners' needs, thereby promoting a supportive learning environment that encourages risk-taking and experimentation.

Social interaction and collaboration: interactive activities often involve social interaction and collaboration among learners, fostering a sense of community and belongingness. By working collaboratively with peers, learners can exchange ideas, share perspectives, and negotiate meaning, leading to deeper understanding and enhanced motivation.

Research by Johnson and Johnson suggests that cooperative learning structures, such as group projects or problem-solving tasks, promote positive interdependence and mutual accountability among learners, resulting in higher levels of motivation and engagement. Moreover, social interaction and collaboration contribute to the development of interpersonal skills and intercultural competence, preparing learners for real-world communication situations.

Personalization and relevance: interactive activities can be tailored to learners' interests, preferences, and proficiency levels, making the learning experience more personalized and relevant. By incorporating authentic materials, real-life scenarios, and learner-centered tasks, interactive activities provide context-rich learning experiences that resonate with learners' experiences and goals.

According to Deci and Ryan, personalization enhances intrinsic motivation by satisfying individuals' psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Interactive activities that allow learners to make choices, set goals, and pursue their

interests empower them to take ownership of their learning and engage more deeply with the material.

Conclusion: Self-Determination Theory and Social Cognitive Theory offer valuable frameworks for understanding and promoting motivation in the tourism field of education. By incorporating autonomy-supportive practices, fostering a sense of relatedness, enhancing students' self-efficacy beliefs, and facilitating observational learning experiences, educators can create engaging and meaningful learning environments that inspire students to pursue successful careers in the dynamic and evolving tourism industry.

Interactive activities play a crucial role in enhancing motivation and engagement in language learning by promoting active participation, providing immediate feedback, fostering social interaction, and personalizing the learning experience. By incorporating a variety of interactive activities into language teaching pedagogy, educators can create dynamic and stimulating learning environments that inspire learners to achieve their full potential.

References:

1. Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall, Inc.
2. Bandura, A. (1997). "Self-efficacy: The exercise of control." Freeman.
3. Chen, C., & Hashimoto, A. (2018). "An exploratory study of self-determined motivation in tourism education." *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 23, 44-52.
4. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). "Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior." Plenum Press.
5. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
6. Dörnyei, Z., & Ushioda, E. (Eds.). (2013). "Motivation, language identity and the L2 self." *Multilingual Matters*.
7. Ellis, R. (2008). "The Study of Second Language Acquisition." Oxford University Press.
8. Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). "The power of feedback." *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112.
9. Holec, H. (1981). "Autonomy and foreign language learning." Oxford: Pergamon Press.
10. Jamal, T. B., & Getz, D. (1995). Collaboration theory and community tourism planning. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 22(1), 186-204.

11. Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (1994). "Learning together and alone: Cooperative, competitive, and individualistic learning." Prentice Hall.
12. Kim, T. Y. (2009). "Motivational variables in second language acquisition: A study of Korean high school students' motivation and attitudes towards learning English as a foreign language." *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 22(2), 115-132.
13. Kim, B., & Pearce, P. (2018). "Exploring the influence of satisfaction on students' career intention: The case of tourism education." *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 18(2), 87-103.
14. Kim, H., Gursoy, D., & Lee, S. (2018). "The relationships between students' academic motivations and their academic performance in a tourism higher education context: Evidence from a mixed-methods approach." *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 23, 1-13.
15. Kramsch, C. (1993). "Context and Culture in Language Teaching." Oxford University Press.
16. Lee, J. S., & Crompton, J. L. (1992). Measuring involvement: A profile analysis of the Greater Orlando Area. *Journal of Travel Research*, 31(4), 3-10.
17. Noels, K. A., Pelletier, L. G., Clement, R., & Vallerand, R. J. (2000). "Why are you learning a second language? Motivational orientations and self-determination theory." *Language Learning*, 50(1), 57-85.
18. Nunan, D. (1999). "Second language teaching & learning." Heinle & Heinle.
19. Oxford, R. L., & Shearin, J. (1994). "Language learning motivation: Expanding the theoretical framework." *Modern Language Journal*, 78(1), 12-28.
20. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). "Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes." Harvard University Press.
21. Wong, K. K. F., & Chon, K. (2010). "An exploratory study of student motivation for tourism education: A case study in Hong Kong." *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 9(1), 21-31.
22. Zimmerman, B. J. (2000). "Self-efficacy: An essential motive to learn." *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 82-91.